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**Implementation of a new technique to improve
subglottic secretion mobilization in tracheotomized
ICU patients: The "volcano method"**

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Publikation

Implementation of a new technique to improve subglottic secretion mobilization in tracheotomized ICU patients: The "volcano method"

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Running head: Implementation of a new technique for secretion mobilization

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ABSTRACT (299 words)

Background

Ventilator associated pneumonia is one of the challenging complications in tracheotomized patients. One key problem is effective drainage of subglottic secretion due to lack of secretion mobilization. We therefore implemented a new method for subglottic secretion clearance. In the so-called volcano method, air is insufflated through subglottic suction line of tracheostomy tube, to blow secretion up to pharynx and mouth, to suction it from there.

Objective

To describe the clinical implementation process of volcano method, including patient allocation according to a defined decision tree. A second objective was to assess ICU health care professionals' knowledge and opinion about newly implemented volcano method.

Methods

Mixed-methods implementation study, consisting of three-step procedure. The first step was a preparatory phase with development of educational material and processes. The second step was a three-months pilot-testing phase with description of patient selection and conduction of volcano method. Finally, a survey on health care professionals' knowledge and opinion about the volcano method was performed using a Likert-scale questionnaire.

Results

Key aspects of the preparatory phase were the development of a standardized operating procedure and an educational video on the volcano method. During the three-month pilot-testing phase, 56 patients were admitted to the ICU, and 10 (18%) were finally treated using the volcano method. Out of the 85 employees of the ICU, 36 (42%) filled out and returned the questionnaire. Most health care professionals strongly agreed on the feasibility and effectiveness of this method, felt confident with the maneuver, while most of them had no knowledge about this method before implementation.

Conclusions

This study successfully shows how a new method in draining the subglottic secretion can be established in a multi-disciplinary ICU team within a short period of time. Further research is needed to evaluate concrete effects on secretion clearance and associated ventilator associated pneumonia.

Key Words:

critical care, mechanical ventilation, ventilator associated pneumonia, tracheostomy, suction, vocalization, ventilator weaning

INTRODUCTION (Manuscript: 3221 words)

Ventilator associated pneumonia (VAP) is one of the major clinical challenges among ventilated intensive care unit (ICU) patients. The incidence for VAP varies widely from 5 to 40% depending upon the setting.¹ It is well-known that VAP increases mortality, prolongs ICU and hospital length of stays, with prolonged ventilation days and thus increases the health care costs.^{2,3} VAP is associated with worse prognosis, when diagnosed in ICU patients, and mortality rates range from 12-48%.^{4,5}

The risk factors that determine the onset of VAP have been thoroughly classified and researched. A major determinant of VAP is mechanical ventilation longer than 20 days. The patients' underlying disease, that determines the length of mechanical ventilation, has a direct impact on VAP incidence.⁶ Similarly, another factor is the type of tracheostomy tube (or endotracheal tube) used during mechanical ventilation. Cannulas or tubes with subglottic secretion drainage (SSD) can reduce the early onset of VAP by up to 45%.⁷ Other major risks include patient's age, immunosuppression, protective swallowing reflex, pre-occurrence of respiratory diseases, prolonged intubation time, re-intubation, and sedation.⁸ To address these risk factors, VAP-bundles were commonly implemented in ICUs.^{9,10} Nevertheless, VAP prevention remains challenging, as there is no gold standard technique and many different interventions are combined in a VAP bundle. One essential intervention proposed in VAP bundles is SSD.¹¹

SSD plays an important role in the prevention of VAP, has a favorable impact on VAP-Incidence rates and is associated with a significant decrease in VAP.^{7,12,13} However, implementation of SSD has limitations, as it depends on numerous factors. The most important being the amount of secretion produced by the patients, their inability in managing the secretion produced owing to certain factors such as analgo-sedation, reduced functional sensibility of the laryngeal parts involved in swallowing and therefore a reduced swallowing frequency. Similarly other factors include practice among ICUs in secretion management, efficiency and efficacy in such practices depending upon individual share done by each nursing ICU-staff. Individualized management, based on the volume of subglottic secretions produced by patients, can further optimize the airway management, and reduce the risk of adverse events of subglottic secretion aspiration.¹⁴ Unfortunately, there is no gold standard defined, how the subglottic secretion present above the cuff can be drained best. In current ICU practice, suctioning is performed through the subglottic catheter wing of specialized endotracheal tubes or tracheal cannulas.

Our clinical evidence suggests, that with common suctioning techniques through this subglottic catheter wing, no sufficient cleaning of the trachea may be reached. Also, it has been seen in clinical use, that depending upon the quantity of subglottic secretion as well as its viscosity, the existing secretion often can't be completely removed by suctioning through the tube. Therefore, we suggest an alternative technique, in which mucus residing in the subglottic region, above the cuff, is blown up into the mouth and then suctioned from there. Like a volcanic eruption, the injected air would lift the secretion through the vocal cords. Therefore, we suggest the name "volcano method" for this technique. This method is not completely new and has been practiced by speech and language therapists in patients with tracheostomy tubes during above cuff vocalization (ACV)¹⁵ but with a completely different goal. Interestingly, a higher amount of secretion mobilization has been noticed as a side effect by our speech and language therapists as well as the attending physicians in clinical practice. Therefore, we hypothesize, that clinical implementation of this volcano method is feasible to optimize secretion management, in a specific group of tracheotomized ICU patients. The concrete aims of this study were 1) to develop a standardized operating procedure (SOP) for the clinical use of the volcano method; 2) to describe the patient's selection process for application of this method; and 3) to assess the ICU health care professionals' knowledge and opinions on the volcano method.

METHODS

This mixed-methods implementation study was conducted in the ICU setting of a large neurologic rehabilitation hospital in Switzerland, with ten beds for ventilated patients. This ICU is specialized in patients with spinal cord injuries or difficult airway procedures and prolonged weaning sessions. Our study collected qualitative and quantitative measures over the whole implementation period of this new volcano method, which lasted from May 2024 until end of November 2024. Within this timeframe, a three step implementation procedure was conducted:

- I. Preparatory phase:** development of educational material and processes (SOP)
- II. 3-months pilot-testing:** patient selection and conduction of the volcano method
- III. survey:** a qualitative assessment on ICU health care professionals' knowledge and opinion about the volcano method

These three steps are described in detail below:

- I. Preparatory phase:** before practical implementation of the volcano method in the ICU, the following steps were conducted.
 - i. Project presentation and approval from the internal "Breathing Advisory Board" consisting of internal physicians, nurses, speech and language therapists.
 - ii. Development of the SOP "volcano method" (Supplement 1)
 - iii. Preparation of an SOP based training video for the ICU health care professionals
 - iv. Hands-on-training for the ICU health care professionals
 - v. Advise physicians to prefer tracheal cannulas with a subglottic tube

Conduction of these five steps were done within approximately three months, between May and July 2024.

II. 3-months pilot-testing phase:

The aim of this pilot-testing phase was to get an estimate about the percentage of all ICU patients eligible for treatment and to get a first impression about the feasibility of the volcano method. The preconditions, among ventilated and tracheotomized patients for application of the volcano method were:

- swallowing disorder with a Penetration-Aspiration-Scale-Score >7 ¹⁶
- high amount of secretion production
- an appropriate tracheal cannula with a subglottic secretion wing

All ICU admissions between 1st of August 2024 and 31st of October 2024 were screened for eligibility to conduct the volcano method, according to the decision tree presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: decision tree on patient allocation to the volcano method

The concrete procedure including devices and preconditions to conduct this method is described below.

Volcano-procedure and operative preconditions:

Air insufflation through the suction tube was applied using the oxygen supply present in the respective ICU rooms (a.). The oxygen flow could be regulated through an analogue valve regulator (b.). Turning the regulator wheel anticlockwise increased the flow and turning it clockwise reduced the flow. A flow of 2-3 liters per minute was sufficient for the regurgitation of the subglottic secretion. The air blown in was regulated and adjusted according to patient's tolerance. The oxygen flow could be increased, when needed, up to 6 liters per minute. The analogue valve regulator supplying oxygen was connected via a plastic tube with an adapter (c.). The adapter (d.) has a fingertip regulator (e.) for the fine adjustment of the air flow into the suction drainage tube (f.) of the respective tracheal cannula (g.). Finally, the mobilized secretion was suctioned pharyngeal and oral using a suction tube (Charrière, size CH14). Before the procedure was applied, the respective patient's oral secretion was suctioned via mouth thoroughly. The volcano method was performed bedside by the patient's attending ICU nurse, whilst a second nurse in charge was responsible for the oxygen flow regulations. The total time needed for the procedure was about 3-5 minutes and was performed once about every eight hours.

Figure 2 A: Technical setup required for application of the volcano method, and 2 B: addition with fingertip application for finer flow adjustment. Legend: a.) room oxygen supply; b.) analogue oxygen valve regulator; c.) oxygen flow tube to patient; d.) adapter (Spiggle & Theis, single use suction handles); e.) fingertip regulator; f.) suction drainage tube; g.) tracheal cannula (Traceo, with subglottic suction aid)

III. Survey

An anonymized qualitative assessment of health care professionals' knowledge and opinion on the volcano method was drafted for the four involved groups working on the ICU: nurses, physicians, speech and language therapists, and physiotherapists. The questionnaire consisted of the following seven questions:

1. Are you familiar with subglottic suctioning?
2. Did you have any prior knowledge regarding the volcano method before its introduction in the ICU?
3. Were the SOP and the video introduction to the volcano method helpful in its practical implementation?
4. Is the volcano method practically easy to perform?
5. After the three month introductory period, do you feel confident in performing the volcano method?
6. Do you think that the volcano method can contribute to secretion mobilization in addition to subglottic suctioning?
7. Do you think that the volcano method can contribute to reducing ventilator associated pneumonia in our patients?

For each question the following answer options were given on a 6-point Likert-scale: strongly agree (1); somewhat agree (2); neither agree nor disagree (3); somewhat disagree (4); strongly disagree (5); don't know (6)

The questionnaire was printed on paper and placed in the common room of the ICU, where all the employees of the ICU had access to. A collection shelf for anonymously filled questionnaires was also placed nearby. All employees of the ICU were informed orally and by E-mail to fill out this questionnaire. After a week of dispatch, a reminder was initiated via internal newsletter.

The questionnaire collection period was from November 1st until November 15th, 2024.

Statement of Ethics and study approval:

The research described in this study was conducted in accordance with the World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki.¹⁷ Based on the Swiss law and the Swiss Human Research act, this qualitative study does not fall within the scope of the Swiss Human Research act and therefore needed no specific ethics approval. The ethics committee north-west and central Switzerland (EKNZ) confirmed this under the number: Req-2024-00607.

RESULTS

The first step, to implementation of this new method, in improvement of secretion clearance has primarily been initiated by ICU physicians, with strong support from speech and language therapists. People familiar with this method, which included physicians as well as speech and language therapists, prepared the SOP, produced an educational video, and executed the hands-on training for the nurses.

During the three months pilot-testing phase of the volcano method, 56 patients were admitted to the ICU. The patient selection process for application of the volcano method is shown in the flowchart of Figure 3 and has been conducted according to the decision tree shown in Figure 1 (methods).

Figure 3: Flow-chart of ICU patient selection for application of the volcano method

Overall, 10 patients or 18% of all admitted patients to the ICU and 50% of all ventilated patients were finally treated with the volcano method. A key-component to conduct the volcano method was selection of an adequate type of cannula with a subglottic suction tube. Eleven patients had to undergo a cannula exchange before this method could be applied. These patients were admitted to the ICU with various diagnoses. But common key problems were prolonged weaning, massive swallowing disorders, primary and secondary neurological disorders related to weak oro-tracheal and diaphragmatic function.

The survey on the opinion and knowledge about the volcano method, performed among health-care professionals working in the ICU, showed a good response rate of 44%. The exact numbers of employees and their response rates, overall and for each health care profession separately, are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Number of ICU employees overall and per professional group with response rates on the questionnaire.

Group	Employees (N)	Responses (N/%)
Overall	85	36 / 42%
Nurses	65	30 / 46%
Physicians	13	3 / 23%
Physiotherapists	4	3 / 75%
Speech therapists	3	0 / 0%

The responses generally showed a very positive opinion about this new method. Responses to the seven questions listed in the methods section are presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4: overview on the responses to the survey on the volcano method

DISCUSSION

This study describes a successful three step implementation procedure of the volcano method for the improvement of SSD in a multi-disciplinary ICU team. This mixed-methods study provides a concrete description of the volcano method and an example of how such a method can be implemented within six months, in a complex multi-disciplinary ICU setting. Once implemented and health care professionals trained, this method can be applied with only about five minutes of additional time per patient and treatment session. In our setting, 18% of all ICU admissions and 50% of all ventilated patients were qualified for application of the volcano method. The general attitude of health care professionals after implementation of the volcano method was very good, even if most of them had no knowledge about this method before implementation.

A key predisposition for such a successful implementation may have been a general agreement on the importance of this new treatment method, as well as the willingness of all team leaders, along with the head physicians, to make an additional effort. This involved developing the SOP, preparing educational videos and providing clinical hand-on-support and motivation for the whole team. Similarly, the extensive experience in cannula management among the health care professionals also played an important role in the smooth implementation of such a new method. Additionally, the detailed and regular interdisciplinary teamwork provided a good functional background. The initial idea of SSD using the volcano method came from a long-term observation of secretion mobilization by speech and language therapists, as a byproduct of ACV. ACV has been used internationally for years and has been established as a safe method for initiating, activating, and maintaining the involvement of laryngeal organs in speech production throughout the ventilation period.^{15,18,19} Thus, there is no need to prove the clinical safety of this method again.

As obvious it is, that SSD plays a very important role in VAP prevention in the ICUs, it is not obvious that the management of SSD is an easy and routine procedure.^{13,14} This highly depends on the respective ICU-settings and the ICU staff/nurse experiences. ACV is not a new method for our speech and language pathologists, which builds up the basics for the volcano method.^{15,18,19} Yet it was initially not an easy task to establish the pre-implementation procedure, as well as to practically implement this clinical procedure. Also, the eminence-based handling, among the health-care professionals, was a very important preliminary bias. An important discussion among the ICU staff was the idea, that tracheal cannulas with suction aid would prolong weaning, as different cuffs used in such cannulas (size and structure) would increase irritation in patient's tracheal parts and thus have adverse effects. But comprehensive and regular support from speech therapists as well as strict instructions to follow the SOP were the main facilitators that improved the implementation of volcano method. Once these basic aspects as well as their importance convinced the health-care professionals, implementation proceeded smoothly.

Once the patient's initial problem of prolonged respiratory deficiency is overcome, with the help of tracheostomy, these patients are ventilated using an adequate

cannula. After that, cannula management is a top priority and needs a lot of experience. Based on this experience and the different clinical features: patient's swallowing criteria - intensively evaluated by the speech and language therapists, neurological disorders, overall muscular function and a day-to-day re-evaluation of these aspects, an appropriate cannula, to overcome the momentary functional deficits of the patient, is chosen. Depending upon the above stated features, the appropriate cannula for the respective patient does not always need to be the one with a suction aid. Despite these strict and various preconditions, 77% of all volcano eligible patients finally underwent this new procedure.

Our analysis of the patient selection procedure showed approximately 50% of tracheotomized patients qualified for treatment with volcano method. After the initial training period and an additional three month pilot testing period, the ICU health care professionals responsible for this new method (nurses and physicians) had positive opinion on the volcano method, which seems to be an important facilitator in such an implementation process.

Our 42% response rate to the survey from the ICU health care professionals involved (Table 1) was quite good and within the range of other comparable surveys in ICU settings.^{20,21} Overall 46% ICU-Nurses, 23% ICU-Physicians and 75% ICU-Physiotherapists responded to our survey. Surprisingly, the speech and language therapists' responses lacked. Unfortunately, it was because of an underlying communication gap with the speech and language therapists. Analyzing responses, the health care professionals had good prior knowledge about subglottic secretion management, but the volcano method seemed to be completely new to these persons too. They found SOP implementation as well as video trainings very helpful and seem to be convinced that the practical implementation process was quite easy. From our point of view, the questionnaire exactly reflects the practical learning curve the ICU staff gained after the implementation period. The efficiency of implementation was welcomed positively by the ICU nurses. Furthermore, the ICU-staff/nurses involved were convinced that the volcano method could positively help with secretion mobilization, since they could often observe a bigger amount of oral secretion suctioned after the application of volcano method. Thus, this paves a way for a next study which could quantify the amount of sputum that could be drained using the volcano method. In conclusion, the more volcano method helps in successful subglottic drainage, the more it could help in preventing VAP incidence. This again paves a way for a study that could compare the VAP incidence before and after implementation of the volcano method.

Strengths and limitations

The patient selection process, as seen in the flow chart (Figure 3), is very specific for ICU conditions at the hospital where this study was performed, where the respiratory weaning process is indeed a core problem among a high percentage of their ICU patients. Thus, it may not represent the ICU conditions of other institutions, but there

is no limitation that prevents volcano from being applied among other tracheostomy patients. The results clearly state that this method can be applied to a substantial percentage of the tracheostomized patients of an ICU.

The overall questionnaire response of 42% was quite good. This mainly reflects the response rate of the largest group of ICU nurses with 46%, while the response rate of ICU physicians was only 23% and therefore less representative. The 75% response rate of the physiotherapists ought to be evaluated very critically, since this is a very small group, and they were basically not directly involved in the practical implementation procedure of the volcano method. Surprisingly there were no responses received from the speech and language therapists. This would have been very interesting, since they played an important role in developing the SOP as well as training the ICU staffs. This was due to lack of an effective information flow among the speech therapists in the ICU department. The different channels of communication we used didn't unfortunately reach the team of speech and language therapists. It would also have been very important to know patient's feelings and tolerance towards this new method. However, most patients treated with this method could not communicate properly because of their laryngeal organ dysfunctions.

Conclusion

The volcano method can be clinically well implemented among the ICU patients if the ICU staff/nurses are trained and helped respectively. Around 50% of ventilated patients may qualify for the application of this method and potentially profit from improvement of subglottic secretion clearance. ICU physicians and nurses are key health care professionals for implementation of this method and proper training of these professional groups seems to be important for a smooth and successful implementation procedure. Further research is needed to evaluate concrete effects on secretion clearance and associated pulmonary infections, such as pneumonia.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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None

Author Contributions

BN is the principal investigator of this project. BN, LB, and GM designed the study, and all authors listed made substantial contributions to the conception or design of the work. GM provided methodological support in the study design. LB and RL provided clinical support. BN drafted the work. All authors of this manuscript revised it critically for important intellectual content and gave final approval to the version to be published. All authors agreed to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved.

Data availability

Data will not be placed in a repository to protect participant privacy but can be made available upon reasonable request.

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Supplement SOP Volcano Method:

SOP – Volcano Method

Indication:

- Mobilization of secretion (Secretion present subglottic or above the cuff) before deblocking tracheal cannula

highly infectious
saliva accumulation

Precept:

- Efficient method for mobilization of secretion present subglottic or above the cuff before deblocking tracheal cannula
- Insufflation of oxygen through subglottic suction tube and thus mobilization of secretion in the mouth/throat region
- Requirement: Tracheal cannula with subglottic suction tube

Implementing staffs:

- through staffs, who are authorized to perform endotracheal suctioning

Relative contraindication:

In the following cases extra caution is needed!

- fresh tracheostoma (first 5 days after installation, risk for soft tissue emphysema)
- airway shift/obstruction in region above the tracheal cuffs, i.e.
 - pronounced swelling
 - paralysis of vocal folds on both sides in median and/or paramedian position

Practical implementation:

- verify cuff's impermeability, perform aspiration test over the subglottic suction tube
Notice: during the subglottic suction instruct patient to inhale and exhale through the mouth (not to hold the breath), this opens the vocal folds and thus prevents a vacuum under the vocal folds
- connect the tracheal cannula suction line/tube with the fingertip adapter and the oxygen tube
- start oxygen insufflation in 2 steps:
 1. start with a low flow of 1-2 l/min
 2. increase the flow up to a max. 6 l/min
- Hint: auscultation above the tracheostoma helps to verify if secretion/saliva is present
- stop air/oxygen insufflation after the successful implementation, documentation in software "IMESO" under "suction" --> "volcano"
- Cave:

- oxygen connector must be in reach, near to the patient (oxygen connector at the back of the pillar is not suitable as it is too far)
- oxygen/air insufflated must flow out of the nose or mouth --> if not, the procedure must be stopped immediately (risk of emphysema)
- take caution of vagal reaction --> stop immediately
- fingertip can be used to control the flow and thus an overpressure can be minimized

Necessary equipment:

1. tracheal cannula with a subglottic suction line (suction aid; e.g. Tracoe Vario, Portex BlueLine), recognizable on its two tubes (subglottic working canal connected with a closure flap and as usual a connecting tube to the cuff with a ventil ballon)

2. Fingertip ("connector/adapter")

3. Bedside oxygen connector

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